

Decentering the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Return Migration Infrastructures in Tunisia

Country Dossier (WP3)

Authors:

Hassen Boubakri, Hanen Ben Othmen, Malak Jedidi

University of Sousse

Funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by

UK Research
and Innovation

Canada Excellence
Research Chair in
Migration & Integration

Deliverable Information

Project acronym	Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond
Project no.	101094341
WP	3
Deliverable title	Return Migration Infrastructures in Tunisia
Deliverable type	R – Document, report
Version	V2
Date	July- 2025
Responsible partners	University of Sousse
Authors	Hassen Boubakri, Hanen Ben Othmen, Malak Jedidi
Dissemination level	Public

© USousse

This research was conducted under the Horizon Europe project ‘GAPS: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond’ (101094341). The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to the author at hassen.boubakri@flsh.u-sousse.tn

Cite as:

Boubakri, H., Ben Othmen, H. and Jedidi, M. (2025). “Return Migration Infrastructures in Tunisia”. WP3 Country Report in GAPS: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. *Working paper 2025/21*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15852188

Contents

1. Executive Summary.....	4
2. Introduction of the Tunisian case study	6
3. Methodology and Data Collection	7
4. Context of Migration and Return Figures.....	8
5. Return Migration Infrastructures	12
6. Actors of RMI.....	15
6.1 Implementation / “doings” of RMI.....	18
6.2. Materials and technologies used in the RMI.....	25
6.3 Relations (interactions and frictions) between actors, materials and technologies in the RMI	28
7. Conclusion.....	37
References.....	38

1. Executive Summary

Tunisia, due to its geographic proximity to Europe and historical emigration trends, serves as a strategic case study to examine the Return Migration Infrastructures (RMI). The Tunisia RMIs include a wide range of institutions, actors, emerging technologies, and ad hoc procedures that govern and facilitate the return of Tunisian nationals abroad—both voluntary and coerced. The study combined desk research, including analysis of secondary sources such as national statistics, surveys, policy briefs, and reports from international organisations, along with insights from fieldwork on returnees. However, accessing data on return migration in Tunisia, worsened by coerced repatriations of Sub-Saharan Africans, remains obscure due to political sensitivity, limited transparency, and restricted access.

Tunisia has experienced various waves of emigration, especially after the 2011 revolution, driven by unemployment, economic instability, and political unrest. By 2024, nearly two million Tunisians lived abroad—mainly in France, Italy, and Germany. Both voluntary returns (due to family or economic reasons) and forced returns of Tunisian migrants (deportations, expulsions) are common. Forced returns are often linked to vulnerabilities, such as irregular status, insecurity, or health issues. Return migration patterns have fluctuated, while the forced returns, particularly from Italy and Germany, have increased in recent years. Deportation often involves detention and is accompanied by allegations of mistreatment, highlighting human rights concerns.

Tunisia's RMI main characteristics are as following.

- It involves a wide network of actors including national ministries (Interior, Social Affairs, Transport, Employment), agencies like the Office of Tunisians Abroad (OTE) and National Observatory of Migration (ONM), as well as international partners such as GIZ (Germany), OFII (France), and IOM.
- The *Tounesna* program is Tunisia's flagship reintegration initiative. It supports returnees—regardless of whether they returned voluntarily or by force—through counselling, job placement, and financial aid. However, only 79 returnees benefited from the program in 2022, reflecting accessibility issues.

- Returnees primarily arrive via airports in Enfidha, Tunis, Djerba, and Monastir. Security dominates the reception process, with returnees often facing interrogation and lacking follow-up support. Tunisia uses biometric systems, but lacks a centralized database for tracking and supporting returnees post-arrival.
- There are major coordination gaps between Tunisian institutions, NGOs, and international partners. NGOs which play a crucial role in protecting returnees' rights, yet remain underfunded and under-recognized.

There are issues surrounding funding and the EU's external influence over Tunisia's return policies. Over the past decade, the EU and member states have directed millions of euros to Tunisia for migration management, mainly focusing on border control. Only a small portion of this funding supports reintegration. This reinforces a security-first approach and restricts the development of sustainable return solutions. Tensions also persist between Tunisian sovereignty and European migration control policies, especially regarding Italy and France, which frequently impose return policies linked to aid or security funding. Authorities prioritize EU interests, often ignoring human rights concerns, while NGOs face barriers to monitoring and research. In summary, Tunisia's return migration infrastructure remains fractured and underdeveloped. A more holistic, rights-based, and coordinated strategy is crucial to ensure the dignified and sustainable reintegration of returnees, whilst remaining sensitive to the side effects of the EU's externalisation and funding in the countries of origin and transit.

2. Introduction of the Tunisian case study

This national report is part of WP3: Migration Return Infrastructure, a key component of the GAPs project. WP3 focuses specifically on migration return infrastructures – a concept that includes the technologies, institutions, and interconnected actors that structure return processes (Xiang& Lindquist 2014). Several key dimensions are identified: the commercial aspect involves the role of intermediaries and recruitment agencies, the regulatory aspect includes administrative procedures, legal frameworks, and bilateral agreements, the technological aspect covers communication, transportation, and surveillance systems like biometrics, the humanitarian aspect highlights the involvement of NGOs and international organizations in aid and reintegration programs and the social aspect focuses on migrant networks and transnational ties that facilitate returns.

Tunisia presents a relevant case study for understanding coerced returns and related infrastructures due to its proximity to Europe and its involvement in regional migration dynamics. Although Tunisia's return migration infrastructure is not yet fully developed, it increasingly relies on international initiatives, especially reintegration programmes supported by global partners. Tunisia's return and readmission systems provides insights for the understanding of broader trends in return migration. Specifically, this report examines the infrastructure for return migration in Tunisia, exploring the socio-economic and political factors that influence it, as well as the interactions among the involved actors. It also highlights the tensions between the different agendas of national and international actors, as well as the difficulties in implementing return policies.

This report starts with presenting trends and figures of return migration, then move to provide a detailed discussion on the actual practices of the relevant actors involved. It demonstrates how return has become maybe more accessible but also more complex. By documenting the realities of return in Tunisia, this analysis contributes to a deeper understanding of the impacts of these practices on migration governance and the trajectories of migrants.

3. Methodology and Data Collection

The WP3 research was conducted between June 2023 and June 2024 and included two main tasks. First is to create an overview of Return Migration Infrastructures (RMIs) in each partner country, such as Tunisia, by producing flow maps through desk research. Desk research included the study of reports, policy briefs, informative leaflets, data reports, newsletters, websites, etc. on the implementation of returns, from involved actors and/or observers. Desk research and the flow maps produced are structured around i) the actors involved, ii) their doings, and iii) the materials and technologies used. Second, the WP3 research focused on selecting a particular RMI type (assisted returns, forced removals, or pushbacks) as a case study. The research started from a specific “entry point” on the ground related to the everyday workings of the RMI selected. It included the implementation of semi-structured interviews in each country with actors involved at the meso-level of the everyday operation of the return procedure, which may both facilitate and contest return operations. All interviewees received an Information Letter and provided either written or oral consent for participating in the research. Partners were also encouraged to conduct ethnographic observations during the interviews or on other suitable occasions, on a voluntary basis.

Data collection on Tunisia's return migration key aspects integrated evidence from various sources, including statistical data, documentary sources and qualitative interviews. The statistical data from the Tunisian National Institute of Statistics (INS), Frontex, and Eurostat form the basis of the analysis in this report. Notably, the Tunisia-HIMS report

¹, published in 2021 by INS in collaboration with the National Migration Observatory (ONM) with the support of the International Centre of Migration Policy Development (ICMPD). The survey offered a comprehensive overview of migration phenomena from the perspective of Tunisians by distinguishing voluntary and coerced returns.

Gathering data on migration in, out, and through Tunisia is a difficult task. It should be recognised that our research took place during a highly sensitive period concerning migration issues within Tunisian society and politics. Despite our efforts, we could not obtain information on return infrastructure or access to the locations and spaces where returns are processed. Although we agreed to serve on the GAPS Panel of Experts and Stakeholders, the Ministry of Interior did not respond to our repeated requests for information on returns. However, the Ministry of Social Affairs was more cooperative

during Work package 8 of the GAPS research, which aims to understand returnees' experiences.

Fortunately, the report incorporated key information from available online sources. We reviewed publications from relevant organisations which have programs about return and reintegration, such as the International Organization for Migration (IOM), Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), the Office of Tunisians Abroad (OTE), EuroMED Rights and others. These materials assisted us in understanding the institutional frameworks and practices related to the reintegration of returning migrants as well as challenges faced by returning migrants.

We want to emphasise that data collection from secondary sources has limitations in fully capturing the range of influential factors and the complexity of return migration dynamics. For example, the HIMS survey data only partially reflects certain intricacies. Additionally, potential bias in international organizations' publications and the limited number of interviews conducted reduce the broader applicability of our findings. Additionally, the scarcity of published data on return migrants and the difficulty in reaching relevant stakeholders complicate the situation and constrain the scope of the interviews. Despite these constraints, our analysis provides a valuable starting point for understanding and addressing the multifaceted issues surrounding migrant returns in Tunisia.

4. Context of Migration and Return Figures

Over the last 25 years, migration from Tunisia has progressed through several phases influenced by political, economic, and social considerations.² Post-revolution economic challenges spurred emigration trends. Furthermore, Tunisia's economy experienced rising unemployment due to the departure of foreign investors amidst political instability and strikes. The COVID-19 pandemic introduced a new wave of migratory pressure, amplified by strict lockdowns, economic stagnation, and increased uncertainty. These issues disproportionately affected small businesses and young entrepreneurs, leading to a rise in irregular migration initiatives.³ Overall, migration from Tunisia has reflected shifts in internal developments, regional conflicts, and global crises, leading to cyclical phases of increased emigration.⁴

In 2024, 1.8 million Tunisians were working and residing abroad. Some 80% of them are in Europe, including 54% in France.⁵ Tunisians primarily reside in three countries:

France, Italy, and Germany; some have reached these countries irregularly. According to informants and numbers on irregularly staying of third country nationals in Europe, irregular emigration of Tunisians is widespread.⁶ For nearly 15 years since the 2011 uprising, at least 200,000 Tunisians have left the country without passing through official border controls. During the same period, no fewer than 150,000 higher education graduates (engineers, computer scientists, doctors, paramedical personnel)⁷ have also exited Tunisia regularly, presenting another challenge for the country regarding the sensitive issue of brain drain.

In this context of emigration including irregular ones to the European countries, both voluntary and coerced returns also happen. Voluntary returns are usually motivated by personal choices, such as family circumstances, employment prospects, or the pursuit of better opportunities in Tunisia. Nevertheless, according to the survey report from the National Institute of Statistics in 2021 (Observatoire National de la Migration, 2023) , the reasons linked to vulnerability are the most common causes of voluntary returns. Coerced returns represent a very different reality. It highlights the complexity of migration trajectories, where decisions to return can be shaped by a range of factors, whether chosen or imposed. For example, according to Tunisia-HIMS report ⁸, migrants returning due to expulsions, deportations, or documentation issues represent 7.8% of cases,⁹ with a higher prevalence among men (8.9%) compared to women (4.1%). This percentage is higher for returnees from European countries (10.1%). Vulnerable situations experienced by migrants in host countries—such as irregular status, lack of integration, insecurity, or health problems,¹⁰ were the main reason for 23.8% of returns. These factors have a significant impact on returns from Libya, with 24.4% of all returns.¹¹ Furthermore, unemployment, poor job conditions, and the expiration of work contracts were cited as reasons for 16% of returns,¹² affecting men (17.4%) more than women (9.1%). These factors influence migrants returning from Middle Eastern countries (35%) and young people under 35 years old (65.6%). Return migration trends and figures reveal important patterns regarding the origins and distribution of returnees, highlighting key areas and countries that play a significant role in return migration dynamics (Boubakri& Potot 2016).

Table 1: Evolution of the number of returning migrants

<u>Period</u>	<u>Effective</u>	<u>Growth rate %</u>
<u>Before 1994</u>	<u>76532</u>	

<u>1995-1999</u>	<u>13593</u>	<u>-82.24</u>
<u>2000-2004</u>	<u>13496</u>	<u>-0.71</u>
<u>2005-2009</u>	<u>18952</u>	<u>40.43</u>
<u>2010-2014</u>	<u>33575</u>	<u>77.16</u>
<u>2015-2020</u>	<u>46000</u>	<u>37.01</u>

According to the National Institute of Statistics, the regions of Greater Tunis, Centre-East, and South-East represent 62.9% of all return migrants. The Centre-West region, particularly the area with the highest number of returnees from Libya (68.7%), accounts for 16.4% of the return migration. On the other hand, the Northwest and Southwest regions are less significant, hosting only 8.2% and 3.1% of the returnees, respectively.

Regarding the returning states, returns from Italy accounts for 11.7%, France for 31.5%, and Libya for 34.3% . Also, countries with less structured migration frameworks, such as Saudi Arabia, Germany, and the UAE, also contribute to return migration, through at smaller percentages. Countries like Canada are also account for a smaller but growing share in returns.¹³Over the years, the statistics reveal changes in migration flows, with a noticeable decline in returns from Libya post-2000, but returns from France remain stable and those from Italy and Gulf countries have risen significantly.¹⁴ Moreover, there are clear gender disparities, especially in Libya, where there are many more male returnees (38.7%) than female returnees (12.2%).

Alongside the Tunisia HIMS Survey on return migration, we have utilised some valuable published data by the FTDES regarding deportation (or coerced returns) of Tunisian nationals from Italy and Germany, which are the countries ranking second and third in deporting Tunisians. We couldn't access the French data, even though France is the primary country of deportation for Tunisians.

Fig.1. Deportation of Tunisian Nationals from Italy to Tunisia by air

Between 2016 and the first semester of 2024 (8.5 years), 16,612 Tunisians returned from Italy on board 565 flights, or an annual average of 1,954 migrants, the vast majority of whom were deported. About Germany, data were available only since 2018, but they cover the whole of 2024 year. Over the seven-year period (2016-2024), 1,757 Tunisians were deported from Germany on board 75 flights, or an annual average of 252 deportations per year.

Figure 2. Deportation of Tunisian Nationals from Germany to Tunisia by air

5. Return Migration Infrastructures

Return Migration Infrastructure is a significant topic and presents serious challenges in Tunisia, as although it is a sensitive aspect of the migratory cycle, it remains overlooked and undervalued by the Tunisian authorities, which is detrimental to returnees and puts them at a disadvantage. This idea will eventually be elaborated upon after mentioning the different categories of returns.

Return is defined by the International Organization for Migration as “the act or process of going back or being taken back to the point of departure. This could be within the territorial boundaries of a country [...] or between a country of destination or transit and a country of origin”.¹⁵ Two main types of return migration are defined as follows: coerced return and voluntary return. Voluntary return is a formal policy defined as “the assisted or independent return to the Country of origin, transit or Third Country, based on the free will of the returnee” (IOM 2019)¹⁶. Voluntary return seems less problematic than the coerced return as the former is seen as the most humane and sustainable form of return.¹⁷ It is usually a cost-effective way to manage return compared to some other restrictive measures such as detention. Under the European Union migration policy, voluntary return is the preferred type of return.

Regarding voluntary returns, information is crucial. Unfortunately, irregular migrants are not always informed of the option to request a voluntary return in a language they understand. This is the case for Tunisian illegal migrants in Italy, where testimonies indicate that the Italian authorities breach their obligation to inform migrants about the possibility of submitting an application.¹⁸ This situation can explain why the percentage of voluntary departures in Italy does not exceed 7%. Besides, the Report of the European Parliament on the Return Directive shows significant variations between the Member States relating to voluntary return: from 96% in Poland to 7% in Spain and Italy¹⁹. When voluntary return fails, the authorities may remove the third-country nationals by force, which entails actions that are sensitive with regard to fundamental rights. The objective here is to restore “order” by expelling the unlawfully staying aliens (Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou 2024). In this case, the return act involves forceful measures such as compulsion and coercion. According to the Return Directive, this encompasses expulsion, which occurs when a decision mandates the alien to leave the country within a few days, removal, which involves forcibly executing the expulsion and deporting the individual, and readmission to the country of origin or a previous

transit country based on a readmission agreement. Tunisia signed a readmission agreement with Italy in 1998, easing the coerced returns of Tunisian nationals.

Coerced return numbers show fluctuations. In 2011, Eurostat figures show that the number of coerced returns to Tunisia increased by 359% compared to 2010.²⁰ Coerced returns progressively decreased by an average rate of 80% between 2012 and 2016. The year 2017 saw a new surge of 133 % more coerced return compared to the previous year. France and Italy were the two countries who forcibly returned more Tunisian nationals from 2011 to 2017²¹. In 2021, 1200 illegal Tunisian migrants were expelled from France. Most of the flights land at Enfidha airport located at Eastern Tunisia.²²

In the pre-removal phase, Tunisian illegal migrants are in most cases subject to detention, which is governed by the article 15 of the Return Directive. This coercive measure must be prescribed by law, necessary, reasonable and proportional to the objectives to be achieved. It should last for the shortest time and could only be justified by a risk of absconding. National legislation transposing the concept of “risk of absconding” varies significantly. Several Member States have established lengthy lists of criteria that justify finding a risk of absconding (Belgium has 11, France 8, Germany 7, and the Netherlands 19)²³. On the contrary, other Member States (Bulgaria, Greece, Poland) do not enumerate the criteria in an exhaustive manner which is less protective for migrants and could lead to differences in the directive implementation²⁴. Besides, the exceptional and preventive nature of the detention requires that Member States apply other less coercive measures. However, the European Parliament Report shows the existence in national legislations of alternatives to detention but in practice these possibilities are not applied.²⁵ In this context, it is important to highlight the crucial role of the European Union Court of Justice in ensuring the uniform interpretation of the European Union law and upholding human rights. In addition to the question of detention, coerced return raises another more delicate issue, which is the possibility of using force while removing the returnees.²⁶ Unfortunately, illegal practices during coerced returns are not rare. They include pushbacks, excessive use of force, ill-treatment of migrants during the return process, and failing to assist migrants in danger, especially at sea. Fabrice Leggeri, the previous executive director, resigned in April 2022 following accusations of misconduct and lack of transparency. FRONTEX has also faced significant criticism for its complicity in the pushbacks of asylum seekers and migrants in distress at sea, violating international human rights and refugee law.²⁷

Despite the high number of Tunisian coerced returnees, there is a general lack of legal provisions applicable to them. The only developed aspect is the readmission agreements, characterised by the lack of transparency. Those agreements are one of the most common Frameworks to facilitate the expulsion of persons who “do not or no longer fulfill the conditions of entry to, presence in or residence in the requesting state”. The cooperation in the area of return between Europe and Tunisia is marked by bilateral agreements with EU member States such as Italy with more than six readmission agreements²⁸, France and Germany as well as with Switzerland.²⁹

Fig.3. First page of the First readmission Agreement between Tunisia and Italy in 1998

Fig.4. First page of the Minutes of the Tunisian-Italian agreement of April 2011

The European Union has shown efforts to sign a readmission agreement with Tunisia. Tunisia typically agrees to re-admit its own nationals, but there are disagreements

between the two parties regarding the readmission of Third Countries Nationals who transited through our country. Tunisia has strongly refused to collaborate on their return as this contradicts its domestic and foreign policy interests.³⁰

Regarding the reception of readmitted Tunisians, there is also a lack of information about their numbers, practices, and measures.³¹ It can be claimed that the return migration infrastructure in Tunisia is underdeveloped. Institutionally, it mainly consists of airports—especially Enfidha and Tabarka airports—and secondary airports like Tunis, Monastir, and Djerba. Transportation options such as buses and custody services for some returnees are also limited. The police and customs are the primary entities interacting with returnees at the airports.³²

Although there is an absence of a monitoring system during the phase of reception,³³ Tunisian authorities appear to be primarily concerned with the security aspect.³⁴ Romdhane Ben Amor, communication manager of the Tunisian Forum for Economic and Social Rights (FTDES), noted that on arrival at the airport, returnees are first subject to an identity check to identify persons wanted by the police or the Tunisian justice system.³⁵ The main actors on this stage are the police who interrogate the returnees by asking the questions such as “from where and how did you migrate” “How did you get the money?” “Who was the middleman?” Some coerced returnees reported that they were subject to verbal and physical violence which is due to the lack of monitoring³⁶. They reported having faced bad treatment. Some others reported having spent a few days in custody while others just paid a fine³⁷.

Following identification by the police forces, the returnees are directed to buses bound for different regions of origin without any planned assistance. They are left to fend for themselves without any financial support, medical insurance, counselling, or follow-up after return.³⁸ Usually, they returned to the governorates where they were living before departure. The return area is the place where the family was located.³⁹

6. Actors of RMI

Actors involved in the Return Migration Infrastructure (RMI) in Tunisia are diverse and reflect the country's commitment to managing migration issues in a structured and effective manner. Tunisian Governmental Institutions include the following units.

- **The Ministry of Interior** through the **Border Police** at the **airports of readmission** of the Tunisian returnees.

- **The Ministry of Transport** through the **Office of Civil Aviation and Airports (OACA: Office de l'Aviation Civile et des Aéroports)**. This Office is the manager of airports and air traffic in Tunisia. Therefore, it is indirectly part of the **RMI**, by airports that receive flights bringing back migrants who return voluntarily or who have been expelled. But the Management of the return moments remains under the control of the Border Police.

-**The Ministry of Social Affairs**: it's at the core of this infrastructure⁴⁰ with some bodies playing a central role in the Migration flows and topics management in Tunisia. Also, the Ministry of Social Affairs operates through various bodies, including the General Committee for Social Promotion (CGPS), which is responsible for the social reintegration. This mission is carried out through two of its departments: the General Directorate of Solidarity and Social Development, and the General Directorate of Prevention and Social Integration.

-**Office of Tunisians Abroad (OTE: Office des Tunisiens à l'Etranger)**.The primary mission of the OTE is to provide the government with the necessary data and resources to develop policies that assist Tunisians living abroad.⁴¹The OTE is the leader of the return migration programme, called "*Tounesna*" (see below). Nine regional offices, coordinated by the OTE, are located in the headquarters of nine "Gouvernorats" (the subnational territorial level of Tunisia's administrative divisions). Are Tunisian Bodies members of these offices?

-The **General Committee for Social Promotion (CGPS: Comité Général de la Promotion Sociale)**. It plays a role in return migration by facilitating the reintegration of returning migrants through social and economic support programs. It helps returnees access vocational training, employment opportunities, and social assistance to ease their transition back into society.

- **The National Agency for Employment and Self-Employment (ANETI: Agence Nationale de l'Emploi et du Travail Indépendant)**. In terms of employment, the National Agency for Employment and Independent Work (ANETI), under the Ministry of Vocational Training and Employment, is a public establishment with legal autonomy, created by Law No. 93-11 of February 17, 1993. It supports small business development and facilitates the reintegration of returning migrant workers into the national economy.⁴²

-The **National Observatory of Migration (ONM: Observatoire National de la Migration)**, established by Decree No. 2014-1930, plays a crucial role in monitoring

migration trends. It collects and analyzes data, conducts research, and collaborates with various stakeholders to design programs aimed at improving the situation of migrants and strengthening their ties to their home country. The ONM also publishes periodic reports and participates in international forums on migration.⁴³ The ONM carried out and published the findings of the in-depth profiles of return migrants, some of the results of which have been cited above.

- The Ministry of Justice and the tribunals may be concerned by returning migrants who are wanted by Tunisian courts or who have been tried and convicted in one of the member countries of the Schengen area.

There are also the bilateral cooperation services of the EU members States operation in Tunisia's RMI. The prominent ones include development cooperation agencies attached to the embassies of these three main countries sending migrants back to Tunisia: the French Office of Immigration and Integration (OFII) of France, *Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit* of Germany (GIZ), and *Agenzia Italiana per la Cooperazione allo Sviluppo* (AICS) of Italy. These three bilateral cooperation entities are part of bilateral or multilateral structures that bring together stakeholders, which include the Tunisian parties on one side and Tunisia's European partners on the other. These partners can be the bilateral cooperation services mentioned above, or European entities such as the European Union, the EU delegation in Tunisia, or the International Centre for Migration Policy Development. (ICMPD).⁴⁴

We contacted the bilateral cooperation services of the other countries mentioned above (Belgium, Netherlands), who responded that they do not handle these cases. Instead, the responsibility for monitoring and supporting Tunisian migrants returning from these countries lies with the cooperation services of the three main sending countries (France, Italy, and Germany). These services are funded by the EU and the Member States.

-The French Office for Immigration and Integration(OFII) plays a key role in supporting the reintegration of Tunisian migrants returning from France. It provides social and professional reintegration programs, offering assistance in finding employment, vocational training, and access to social services. It works closely with Tunisian authorities to ensure a smooth transition for returnees.

-The German Society for International Cooperation (GIZ) supports returnees from Germany by implementing reintegration and capacity-building programs. It focuses on creating sustainable livelihood opportunities, offering

vocational training, and facilitating access to entrepreneurship programs. GIZ also collaborates with the Tunisian government to strengthen migration management frameworks. Furthermore, GIZ offers financial support to migrants, enabling them to establish their own projects for social and economic reintegration.⁴⁵

-The Italian Agency for Development Cooperation (AICD) is involved in supporting the reintegration of returnees from Italy through social, economic, and cultural programs. It helps returnees reintegrate into the local economy by offering job training, financial support for entrepreneurship, and access to local development projects. It also works with local partners to ensure the sustainability of these programs.

Additionally, institutions such as the OFII and the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ) provide further support and assistance, and reintegration of migrants into their home country. Additionally, institutions such as the OFII and the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ) offer additional support for the reintegration of migrants into their home country. For instance, in 2019, GIZ launched the «Migration and Diaspora Program», which focused on regular labor migration and mobility, cooperation with the diaspora, and migration governance.⁴⁶

-The International Organization for Migration (IOM), established in Tunisia in 2001, is a key player in Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) programs.⁴⁷

Together, these institutions form a complex and interconnected network aimed at addressing the challenges of migration while supporting Tunisia's socio-economic development. IOM operates through its **AVRR** programs, which assist returning migrants in creating their own projects.⁴⁸ However, the IOM Tunisia Office stopped sharing information on its website about AVRR for Tunisian returnees from the Schengen area to Tunisia, as well as for nationals of Sub-Saharan countries from Tunisia to their countries of origin.⁴⁹

6.1 Implementation / “doings” of RMI

The actors involved in return migration infrastructures are diverse and can include both public and private actors. This diversity can either facilitate or contest the return.

Among the public institutions involved, the **Ministry of Social Affairs** plays a key role. This role is reflected in its responsibilities for initiating, negotiating and ratifying international agreements, as well as through the departments and entities operating under its supervision. One such entity is the OTE. Beyond its mission to provide essential data and resources for shaping migration policies that support Tunisian

abroad, the **O****T****E** also develops and execute targeted programs, collect and transmit data to the National Observatory of Migration (**O****N****M**), ensure daily reception of citizens, study their complaints and ensure their follow-up, provide information related to investment and benefits granted for project creation.⁵⁰In addition to its mission to collect and analyze migration data, the **O****N****M** monitors migration trends and phenomena and develop the field of research by encouraging studies related to migration and exploring its future horizons.⁵¹

For handling migration through international employment, ANETI, overseen by the Ministry of Employment and Professional Training, offers vital information to emigration candidates, helps Tunisian expatriates re-enter the national economy upon their return, and connects employers with job seekers both in Tunisia and abroad. The Agency for Industry Promotion and Innovation (APII) and the Agency for Agricultural Investment Promotion (APIA) influence return migration indirectly by supporting the economic reintegration of returning Tunisians, especially entrepreneurs and investors. These agencies do not manage return programs directly but foster an enabling environment by providing financial incentives, administrative assistance, and sector-specific guidance. For example, APII provides technical and logistical support to returning entrepreneurs who want to start businesses in industry and services, helping them navigate regulatory processes and access investment opportunities. Similarly, APIA supports returnees interested in agricultural ventures by helping with land acquisition, offering subsidies, and connecting them to funding mechanisms. Both agencies also work with international organisations and diaspora networks to encourage skilled Tunisians abroad to reinvest in Tunisia, thereby connecting return migration to economic development rather than just repatriation. Their involvement in return migration is therefore less about physical repatriation and more about ensuring that returnees—especially those with capital and expertise—can successfully reintegrate by leveraging investment opportunities.⁵²

Many **Civil Society Organization** (CSO) in Tunisia play an active role in migration issues, including human rights NGOs and organizations focused on the rights of Tunisian returnees. Among these, we can mention the **Tunisian League for the Defense of Human Rights (LTDH)**. As a human rights organisation, the LTDH has integrated migration into its mandate, adopting a comprehensive approach to human rights that includes economic, social, and cultural rights. It mainly intervenes in cases of coerced returns, particularly when Tunisian nationals are deported from abroad, ensuring their rights are protected during repatriation, including safeguarding against mistreatment, access to legal representation, and fair administrative

procedures. For voluntary returnees, the LTDH strives to prevent discrimination and legal obstacles upon arrival, advocating for reintegration policies that uphold their economic, social, and cultural rights. Additionally, the organisation assists returnees facing legal issues, such as statelessness or documentation problems, by providing legal aid and urging authorities to ensure access to essential services. Outside national interventions, the LTDH actively participates in international advocacy, raising awareness of restrictive migration policies that may breach human rights. It highlights concerns such as arbitrary detention in transit zones, inhumane deportation conditions, and insufficient reintegration support. While the LTDH does not directly run return programmes, its role is vital in ensuring that returnees' rights are safeguarded and that migration policies adhere to fundamental human rights principles.⁵³ In addition, **Médecins du Monde** provides vital medical and psychosocial assistance to Tunisians and migrants facing extreme vulnerability.⁵⁴

The diversity of these institutions can sometimes limit the effectiveness of aid.⁵⁵ The complexity of multiple organizations with overlapping mandates can delay the implementation of projects for returning migrants due to bureaucratic obstacles, heavy administrative procedures, and contradictory and severe criteria.

Exemplary Returnee Program: *Tounesna (Our Tunisia) Project*

The ***Tounesna project***, established in 2019 to support the operationalisation of Tunisia's National Migration Strategy (SNM). The project aims to provide a comprehensive and coordinated service for returning Tunisian migrants via a network of structures in Tunis, Sfax, and Médenine. Specialized advisors from the OTE welcome, inform, and guide returning migrants, in collaboration with the ANETI and the General Committee for Social Promotion (CGPS)⁵⁶. The project also benefits from the support of the ProGreS Migration Tunisia initiative,⁵⁷ which helps migrants access their socio-economic rights and offers specific reintegration assistance.

To benefit from the support provided by the *Tounesna* project, specific criteria must be met. These include Tunisian migrants living in a European country that is a partner of the *Tounesna* project such as France and Netherlands,⁵⁸ wishing to return voluntarily. These migrants must cover the costs of their return themselves or benefit from a voluntary return assistance program provided by the European state, one of its operators, an international organization, or the Tunisian embassy in that country.

Tunisian migrants residing in a European country that is a partner of the *Tounesna* project, whether they are required to leave the territory or subject to Coerced return

procedures, are eligible for reintegration assistance upon their arrival in Tunisia, with no distinction made between voluntary and Coerced returnees.

Fig.5. Tounesna (“Our Tunisia” in arabic): “Reintegration of Nationals Returning to the Homeland”

Fig.6. Tounesna Partners: France through the Partnership convention signed between the OTE and the OFII on February 2020; **Germany**, through the Partnership convention signed between the OTE and the GIZ on June 2022, with the Netherlands (...), The **Swiss Federation** (...) and with the **IOM**.

Partenaires

- ◆ La France, à travers la convention de partenariat signée entre l'OFII et l'OTE (février 2020)
- ◆ L'Allemagne, à travers la convention de partenariat signée entre la GIZ et l'OTE (juin 2022)
- ◆ Les Pays-Bas, à travers le financement du projet d'appui au Dispositif «PAD» (septembre 2020-décembre 2022)
- ◆ La Suisse, à travers la convention de partenariat signée entre Expertise France et le Secrétariat d'Etat aux Migrations (SEM), dans le cadre du projet ProGreS Migration (novembre 2022)
- ◆ L'Organisation internationale pour les Migrations (OIM), à travers la convention de partenariat signée avec l'OTE (mai 2022)

Fig.7. Tounesna Brochure

OTE
L'Office des Tunisiens à l'étranger a pour mission générale d'offrir des services aux Tunisiens résidents à l'étranger : services administratifs, médiation sociale et interculturelle, activités éducatives et animation culturelle, accompagnement des changements de situation, etc. Ses attachés sociaux, déployés dans les 16 principaux pays d'émigration et sur tout le territoire national, assurent le dialogue entre les Tunisiens expatriés et les institutions nationales. L'OTE conçoit et met en œuvre des programmes adaptés aux différentes composantes de la diaspora : femmes, familles, étudiants, générations issues de l'émigration, compétences tunisiennes à l'étranger, etc.

ANETI
L'Agence nationale pour l'emploi et le travail indépendant est un établissement public placé sous la tutelle du ministère de la Formation professionnelle et de l'Emploi. Elle a pour principale mission la mise en œuvre de la politique du gouvernement relative à la promotion de l'emploi. Parmi ses nombreuses missions, l'ANETI dispense l'information et l'orientation nécessaires en matière de recherche d'emploi et de formation, notamment dans le cas de la réinsertion dans l'économie nationale des travailleurs émigrés après leur retour définitif.

CGPS
Le Comité général pour la promotion sociale est une institution relevant du ministère tunisien des Affaires sociales. Il est notamment en charge de mener la politique nationale de protection sociale, de participer à la mise en œuvre des programmes de lutte contre la pauvreté et l'exclusion sociale, d'élaborer la politique de sécurité sociale, de favoriser la promotion socio-économique et l'accès aux services sociaux de base des populations vulnérables, et d'assurer la protection sociale en faveur des populations vulnérables.

Agences de mise en œuvre
Expertise France
Expertise France est l'agence publique française de coopération technique internationale. Elle conçoit et met en œuvre des projets contribuant au développement équilibré des pays partenaires conformément aux objectifs de développement durable (ODD) de l'agenda 2030 et aux priorités de l'action extérieure de la France. La mission d'Expertise France est de répondre à la demande de pays partenaires qui veulent renforcer la qualité de leurs politiques publiques pour relever les défis environnementaux, sociaux, économiques ou sécuritaires.

OFII
L'Office français de l'immigration et de l'intégration est un établissement public relevant du ministère de l'Intérieur. Il remplit les missions suivantes : la gestion des procédures régulières d'immigration, l'accueil et l'intégration des immigrés autorisés à séjourner durablement en France, l'accueil des demandeurs d'asile, l'aide au retour et à la réinsertion des étrangers dans leurs pays d'origine. L'OFII dispose de bureaux dans huit pays en dehors de la France : Arménie, Cameroun, Mali, Maroc, Roumanie, Sénégal, Tunisie et Turquie.

Coordination : Expertise France - OFII
Textes : Rachid Cheff
Photos : Rachid Cheff - OFII
Mise en page : Skander Merchaoui

TOUNESNA
تونسنا

DISPOSITIF DE RÉINSERTION DES MIGRANTS
إدماع المعادين

Fig.8. How Tounesna works?

How the National Multi-Institutional System Works:

- The Reintegration System may provide support to returning migrants in their dealings with other public institutions.
- The Reintegration System may coordinate social and/or economic reintegration assistance programs.

Different Categories of Support:

Social Assistance

Employment Assistance

- This assistance may take the form of training or financial incentives for recruitment for companies.
- Monitoring and support from a local monitoring operator for 12 months.

Assistance with project creation.

Development of a business plan, purchase of equipment, administrative procedures, training, and monitoring and support from a local monitoring operator for 12 months.

Additionally, Tunisian migrants who have returned to Tunisia within the last 12 months from a European country that contributes to the Emergency Trust Fund and is a partner of the *Tounesna* project may access this support, provided they are registered in the project's database, meet the eligibility criteria, and funds are available.⁵⁹ These strict criteria have made the project less accessible, explaining why only 79 Tunisians benefited from it in 2022. Since early 2023, 35 applications have been approved, which remains a relatively small number compared to the total Tunisians who returned, either voluntarily or forcibly, from various countries worldwide.⁶⁰

The relative success of the programme relies on effective coordination mechanisms that connect institutional, associative, and international actors to provide comprehensive support for returnees. Coordination is realised through multi-stakeholder collaboration, resource-sharing, and structured partnerships with NGOs, government agencies, and international organisations. To facilitate this, program managers establish formal agreements and working groups with partners specializing in health, social development, and economic reintegration. These agreements define

roles, responsibilities, and action plans to ensure smooth cooperation. Additionally, regular meetings, workshops, and training sessions are organized to align strategies and share best practices among stakeholders. On a logistical level, the program enhances data-sharing systems and case management tools to track returnees' progress and ensure they receive tailored assistance. This includes mapping available resources, streamlining administrative procedures, and improving access to essential services. Moreover, joint advocacy efforts and funding mobilization help sustain long-term reintegration initiatives by influencing policies and securing financial support. By reinforcing these coordination efforts, the program not only improves service delivery but also accelerates the socio-economic reintegration of returnees, ensuring they receive holistic and sustainable support.⁶¹

Tounesna is not the only program of its kind in Tunisia. Other initiatives, such as those managed by the **IOM (International Organization for Migration)**, **UNHCR**, or NGOs like **Caritas**, also provide support to migrants, focusing on emergency aid, job placement, and legal counseling.

Regarding GIZ, the agency does not have a dedicated return migration programme in Tunisia. GIZ mainly concentrates on broader development initiatives, such as job creation, economic development, and capacity building. These projects can indirectly support returnees by creating economic and social opportunities for them, but the process is often slowed by lengthy approval cycles, which require numerous documents and permissions from various institutions such as the Ministry of Social Affairs, the Ministry of Employment and Vocational Training, and others. These procedures frustrate returning migrants who are eager to rebuild their economic and social lives.

On the positive side, these programs offer a wide range of services, from healthcare and legal support to investment advice, which can contribute to successful reintegration when the system functions efficiently. For example, Médecins du Monde medical and psychosocial care addresses immediate vulnerabilities, and GIZ's financial aid helps migrants establish sustainable businesses. However, coordination between these agencies remains a challenge. However, the fragmented and often bureaucratic nature of their collaboration can undermine their overall effectiveness, creating barriers to rapid support for returning migrants.

6.2. Materials and technologies used in the RMI

The European Union continues to improve its infrastructure for returning migrants to their home countries. Italy is the leading “efficient” actor among EU Member States, not only as one of the main countries involved in the repatriation of Tunisians to their

homeland but also as the primary EU nation providing Tunisian security forces (Coast Guards and Navy) with technology, vehicles, and equipment, as well as funds to support the Tunisian economy. Italy holds particular importance, especially for Tunisian migrants, given the geographical proximity between the two countries and the persistent desire of many Tunisians to reach Europe via Lampedusa.⁶²

The main points of entry for Tunisian returnees expelled from various EU Member States are the airports of **Enfidha-Hammamet**, **Monastir** (on the Eastern Coast), **Djerba-Zarzis** (in the South-East), and **Tabarka** (on the Northern Coast). These airports serve as the primary landing zones for deportation flights carrying returnees from Italy and other EU countries.

Under the *Tounesna* project, designated mechanisms are established at these airports to support returnees upon arrival. These include coordinating reintegration services, providing counseling, and offering legal assistance to facilitate migrants' reintegration into society. In collaboration with European countries, the project ensures that returnees are registered in its database and receive customised reintegration support, such as financial aid, job placement, and vocational training. The airport infrastructure aims to make the process smoother and lessen the frustration often caused by slow approval processes and bureaucratic delays. There isn't any specific center provided for returnees to benefit from temporary accommodation. In most cases, this responsibility falls on individual initiatives or assistance from relatives.

The monitoring of returnees is streamlined through integration with the *Tounesna* project's database, which connects to online platforms developed by countries like Italy. These platforms enable real-time tracking of returnees' information, ensuring that Tunisian authorities and partners can provide tailored reintegration support. This data-sharing system enhances coordination between Tunisian immigration authorities, European embassies, and NGOs, allowing for more efficient services such as job training, financial aid, and legal advice. By utilising this detailed information, the reintegration process becomes more personalised and responsive.⁶³

According to a report produced by REACH and Mercy Corps, some migrants find themselves detained and arrested or are faced with paying fines⁶⁴, which means that the Tunisian authorities focus on the security aspect of returns. In response, since 2017, Tunisian civil society initiatives such as FTDES and the organization "Terre pour Tous" condemned these practices. These efforts are involved by the support of the association Avocats Sans Frontières (ASF), which provide legal consultations to returned

migrants⁶⁵ The lack of support reflects the limited infrastructure for welcoming and reintegrating migrants.

a. Technologies (for example used for administration and surveillance)

Among the technologies, Tunisia employs the biometric system. This system primarily focuses on security and is not specifically designed to systematically track returnees. There is no centralised database dedicated to managing the returnees' processes once they arrive in Tunisia, which results from a lack of follow-up systems. The data collected, including contact details and specific needs, is not combined into a centralised system, leading to fragmented information. For instance, local authorities may use some forms of digital surveillance to manage population movement within their areas, but these technologies remain disjointed at the national level and do not adequately respond to the needs of returnees. Consequently, there is no mechanism to ensure that returnees receive ongoing support or that their reintegration is properly monitored.

The CTA website is seen as a technological tool that showcases the stories of Tunisian returnees from Germany, including Nabiha's experience. A mother of three, she had moved legally to Germany to join her husband, a German-Palestinian. However, she felt unable to pursue her education or start her own business, which led her to return to Tunisia. After her return, she sought support from the CTA, which, in partnership with CEIES, helped her start a library project. Now, Nabiha benefits from economic, social, and psychological stability.⁶⁶

Shared databases between ERRIN and local partners in Tunisia allow for the tracking of reintegration outcomes, enhancing transparency and coordination in reintegration efforts. Furthermore, ERRIN contributes toolkits, methodologies, and training manuals, ensuring that local actors are equipped to implement harmonized reintegration strategies.

However, despite the well-organised financial support and network collaboration, questions arise about the sustainability and long-term effectiveness of these reintegration projects. While the programmes aim to support the social and economic reintegration of returnees, the success of these initiatives is often called into doubt. For instance, according to testimonies from GIZ staff, some reintegration projects fail to deliver lasting social and economic outcomes for returnees, leading to frustration and increasing the risk of re-migration.

6.3 Relations (interactions and frictions) between actors, materials and technologies in the RMI

Return migration management in Tunisia involves various stakeholders, but their interactions are often fragmented and lack consistent coordination. While national and international institutions provide a general framework for reintegration, overlapping responsibilities, rigid procedures, and short-term funding cycles often limit their long-term effectiveness. Public agencies such as ANETI, OTE, and ONM contribute to employment and reintegration services but frequently work in isolation, and international actors like the IOM or bilateral cooperation programmes offer financial and logistical support that remains time-bound and insufficient to tackle the complexity of sustainable reintegration. Conversely, NGOs are vital yet under-recognised actors within the return migration infrastructure. They play a crucial role in filling the gaps left by formal structures, responding swiftly to returnees' immediate needs—such as legal assistance, psychological counselling, or temporary shelter—thanks to their grassroots presence and adaptability. Furthermore, many NGOs are engaged in longer-term, community-based initiatives like vocational training, micro-entrepreneurship, and social reintegration, providing tailored and context-sensitive support that contrasts with more standardised government or donor-led approaches.

Despite the absence of formal cooperation mechanisms, NGOs often build informal partnerships with public institutions to bypass bureaucratic delays and provide more pragmatic responses, although such collaborations remain limited in scope and recognition. The absence of a coordinated national strategy that effectively involves NGOs limits the potential impact of these efforts, causing duplication, inefficiencies, and missed opportunities for collaboration. Ultimately, although their visibility in official return programmes is minimal, NGOs play a crucial role in ensuring that reintegration in Tunisia is more humane, locally rooted, and sustainable. This highlights the importance of establishing structured dialogue and collaborative platforms that incorporate their contributions into the wider migration governance framework.

Tensions in Tunisia's RMI mainly stem from conflicting interests, differing priorities, and pronounced power imbalances between national and international actors. A particularly sensitive issue lies in the relationship between Tunisian authorities and European partners,⁶⁷ notably with Italy. Coerced returns organized by European countries are often perceived by Tunisian civil society as expressions of external

pressure that disregard the rights and socio-economic realities of returnees. NGOs such as the Tunisian Forum for Economic and Social Rights (FTDES) and Avocats Sans Frontières (ASF) have repeatedly denounced these practices, highlighting their coercive nature and the inadequate, sometimes degrading, conditions migrants face upon return. These deportations are not merely administrative procedures but are deeply political acts that reflect unequal power dynamics.

Fig. 9. Poster posted on the FTDES Facebook page denouncing deportations and the border regime

Although the Tunisian state does accept deportees, this acceptance is often contested—both institutionally and socially—as it raises questions about sovereignty, dignity, and Tunisia's bargaining capacity. The power struggle between Tunisia and countries like Italy, or its former coloniser France, exposes a postcolonial undercurrent, where migration governance serves as a proxy for broader geopolitical imbalances. European states, supported by funding and political influence, often implement migration control measures that Tunisia finds difficult to negotiate on equal footing. Consequently, while deportations do take place, they are far from being neutral or uncontested; instead, they highlight the ongoing tensions and conflicts at the core of transnational migration politics.

Fig. 10 & 11. Posters and brochures to prevent and support migrants threatened with deportation in Germany with information and advice (2018)⁶⁸

For his part, the Italian Minister of the Interior in the Meloni government, **Matteo Piantedosi**, regularly publishes posters and text messages on his X network page (formerly Twitter), demonstrating the persistence of his fighting policy irregular migrants and their deportation.

Fig. 12, 13, 14, 15. Publications on X by the Italian Minister of the Interior in the Meloni government, Matteo Piantedosi, about “repatriation” of irregular migrants.

12

MINISTERO DELL'INTERNO

13

MINISTERO DELL'INTERNO

14

3.550 CITTADINI
STRANIERI IRREGOLARI
RIMPATRIATI
NEL LORO PAESE DI ORIGINE
DA INIZIO ANNO
IN COLLABORAZIONE CON L'OIM

MINISTERO DELL'INTERNO

15

Fig. 16, 17, 18. Cover page of an agreement between The Italian Ministry of interior and a transportation services company

Ministero dell'Interno

DIPARTIMENTO DELLA PUBBLICA SICUREZZA
DIREZIONE CENTRALE DELL'IMMIGRAZIONE E DELLA POLIZIA DELLE FRONTIERE

Contratto in modalità elettronica ai sensi dell'art. 18 comma 1 del D. Lgs. 36/2023, a seguito di Procedura negoziata a inviti, ai sensi dell'art. 50 comma 1) lett. b) del D. Lgs.vo 36/2023 per la fornitura di un servizio di noleggio di aeromobile e servizi connessi, per il rimpatrio di circa 20/40 stranieri irregolari scortati da 90/100 operatori di polizia per la tratta Trieste TRS - Roma F.no - Palermo - Tabarka - Roma F.no - Trieste TRS per il 04 febbraio 2025 - CIG B5543DFF79.

16

TRA

Prefetto dott. Claudio GALZERANO, agente in nome e per conto del **Ministero dell'Interno - Dipartimento della Pubblica Sicurezza**, nella sua qualità di Direttore Centrale della Direzione Centrale dell'Immigrazione e della Polizia delle Frontiere, il quale dichiara che l'Amministrazione rappresentata è iscritta alla partita fiscale n. 80202230589, di seguito indicata "*Amministrazione*";

E

Dott.ssa Sylvia Kosekova, giusta procura speciale registrata all'agenzia delle entrate di Milano DP2 il 27.03.2024 al numero 28424 della **PAS - PROFESSIONAL AVIATION SOLUTIONS società a responsabilità limitata**, con domicilio legale in Milano, via Aosta 4, pec pasitalysrl@legalmail.it ove è convenuto che possono essere ad essa notificati tutti gli atti di qualsiasi natura inerenti al contratto, di seguito indicata "Ditta".

17

18

Local NGOs and unions, including the UGTT, often find themselves at odds with certain Tunisian public agencies due to their security-focused approach to return migration. A major point of disagreement is the strong emphasis on security measures during the return process, especially at Tunisian airports. This securitised approach is not merely a matter of institutional policy—it is physically embedded in the technologies and infrastructures that shape the return experience. For example, the use of biometric identification systems, surveillance cameras, digital passenger tracking, and reinforced border control equipment reflects and reinforces the prioritisation of control over care. These technologies are frequently funded or promoted through international cooperation projects, particularly with European partners, as part of broader migration management frameworks. For NGOs and unions, such tools symbolise a systemic focus on monitoring and containment rather than support and reintegration.

The materials and technologies become more than operational tools—they are tangible expressions of political decisions and power relations that depict returnees primarily as security subjects rather than individuals with rights and reintegration needs. For example, returning migrants are frequently subjected to excessive identity checks, which may include detailed interrogations and, in some cases, mistreatment. Migrants are subjected to procedures that feel unjust, with little regard for their rights or well-being. This harsh and pitiless treatment can amplify the trauma that many returnees experience after their journey and disrupt their ability to reintegrate into Tunisian society.⁶⁹ Moreover, the focus on security rather than on providing support for the social and economic reintegration of migrants contributes to a widening gap between the state and civil society. According to HIMS survey local NGOs and unions argue that this approach overlooks the broader needs of returning migrants, such as access to employment, healthcare, and social services.

Tensions also emerge within the Tunisian administration when public institutions have overlapping responsibilities. For instance, the roles of the OTE, ONM, and SEITE often intersect in collecting and analyzing migration data. The absence of proper coordination among these agencies often results in duplicated efforts and reduced efficiency.

Finally, disagreements between international donors and Tunisian authorities add another layer of complexity. While European partners primarily aim to externalise migration management, Tunisian actors criticise the lack of sustainable investments to support the economic and social reintegration of migrants. This divergence in priorities creates a sense of injustice and opposition, ultimately limiting the effectiveness of return programs.

c. Flows of funding, activities, databases, materials between these actors and networks

The financing of return migration programmes is mainly driven by international actors, including the European Union, the IOM, GIZ, and other bilateral and multilateral organisations. These actors play a significant role in creating and managing funds aimed at promoting the economic and social reintegration of returnees. Despite their considerable financial contributions, the allocation of these funds is often inconsistent, influenced more by security priorities than by the actual needs of reintegration programmes.

One of the key frameworks through which return migration is managed is the Integrated Return Management System (IRMS),⁷⁰ supported by the European Commission via the Asylum, Migration, and Integration Fund (AMIF).⁷¹

This system involves some European networks that operate on a voluntary basis and are coordinated by the European Commission and Frontex such as the European Return Integrated Network (EURINT) and the European Return Liaison Officers Network (EURLO). Tunisia is not a formal member of these EU-coordinated networks, but it is indirectly involved through operational partnerships and pilot projects, particularly within the framework of bilateral cooperation and externalized border management. Through these channels, Tunisia becomes a key partner in the implementation of return and reintegration procedures initiated from Europe, particularly with countries such as Italy, Germany, and France. This cooperation often includes logistical coordination with Frontex, support from liaison officers, and reintegration activities co-financed by European funds under the ERRIN umbrella. While Tunisia is not part of the decision-making structure of these networks, it is nevertheless subject to their operational logic, raising questions about power asymmetry, sovereignty, and the extent to which external migration governance frameworks shape domestic practices.⁷² These networks facilitate cooperation between various actors in return migration, enabling the sharing of funding, activities, and resources.⁷³

d. Money, the “sinews of war”: European funds dedicated to migration management, including those reserved for financing return policies.

The Italians “ActionAid” and “IрпиMedia”⁷⁴ have reconstructed the channels and financial infrastructure followed by the Italian credits allocated to Tunisia. They collected information about the amounts disbursed to support the Tunisian Ministry of the Interior, the Tunisian Navy and the IOM in implementing these policies and achieving the objectives set.

Here is a summary of the information collected⁷⁵:

- In the Summer 2020, the Italian Minister of Interior promised €11 million to Tunisia. This amount was allocated in 2020 to the “Repatriation Compensation Fund”, a financial instrument created one year before to supply means and to implement the cooperation with Tunisia

- €8 (eight) million were allocated to the Project called “Support for border control and management of migratory flows in Tunisia”.

- In 2021, a second payment of €7 millions was allocated the same project.
- But before its end, Italy conditioned the finalization of the project with Tunisia's full cooperation in repatriating and readmitting its Nationals “[...] The actual purchase and subsequent delivery of the equipment will be linked to the results obtained by the Tunisian authorities concerning the readmission of Tunisian citizens who are in an irregular situation in Italy, as well as the effective management of irregular migratory flows from Tunisia” (Note of the Italian Ministry of Interior sent to the Tunisian authorities on 20 November 2020).

- In order to “encourage” Tunisia to redouble its efforts, it benefited in 2020 and 2021 from five new projects worth €24 million, of which €19 million were dedicated to Border Control. Projects for the social reintegration of returnees shared the remaining amount with other actions.

-The UN-OPS received funds from Italian Ministry of Foreign Affairs in order to coordinate the repair and maintenance operation on six P350 patrol boats that were donated by Italy to Tunisia in 2014, among twelve ones for a total amount of €16.5 million.

-In 2021, the Tunisian Ministry of the Interior requested Italy to provide equipment valued at €2.5 million. These supplies have proven effective in practice, assisting in the reintegration of returnees.

- In November 2021, the Italian Ministry of Foreign Affairs extended the credit reserved to Tunisia by allocating an additional €8 million to reach a total credit of €15 million over two years.

Finally, according to **a study commissioned by the FTDES⁷⁶, titled “The role of European funding for migration in the violent practices of Tunisian security authorities”**, more than €253 million has been allocated to Tunisia over the two-year period (July 2023-June 2023).. They can be detailed as follows (Garavoglia, 2024. Ibid):

- €17 million was mobilised for the establishment of the SAR Zone and for the supply of new naval means.
- €13 millions mobilised for IMO and the HCR;
- €18 millions for the UN office to control drugs and prevent crimes;
- €18 millions were distributed for the provision of additional naval means.

Finally, €30 millions were channeled into funding the Tunisian authorities under the Memorandum of Understanding of 23 July 2023, 15 December 2023. The 57% of this amount has been devoted to the management of the borders and to security programs,

14% to return, readmissions and to socio-economic integration, 11% to mobility programs, 9% to actions related to human and migrants' trafficking, 6% to forms of protection for migrants and refugees, 2% to the mobilisation of the diaspora for the development and 1% to institutional support and to the reinforcement of capacities building” (extracts from the same study). But the author estimates that **it is thus possible to identify at least €358 million funds mobilized by the EU and its member states to support security and migration policy in Tunisia since 2011.**

However, despite the well-structured financial support and network collaboration, questions arise regarding the sustainability and long-term effectiveness of these reintegration projects. While the programs aim to support the social and economic reintegration of returnees, the success of these initiatives is often questioned. For instance, according to testimonies from GIZ staff, some reintegration projects fail to provide lasting social and economic outcomes for returnees, leading to feelings of frustration and contributing to the risk of re-migration.

d. Implementation gaps between different actors' agendas and actions

Return migration programmes often encounter significant gaps between the strategic goals set by various actors and their actual realisation on the ground. These gaps stem from conflicting priorities among stakeholders, poor coordination, and weaknesses in resource and operational management. A clear example of these challenges is the OTE. According to a report by the Tunisian Court of Accounts, the OTE has faced several structural and financial problems that have limited its ability to achieve its goals. For instance, although the OTE manages two separate budgets, its own budget and a fund for «social and cultural action abroad», significant deficits were recorded, including a shortfall of 8.5 million dinars in 2010. Furthermore, mismanagement of human resources and property purchases made the organization's efforts even less effective. These practices show a clear disconnect between the initial plans and the actions carried out. This disconnect not only highlights the internal limitations of the OTE as an institution, but also mirrors broader gaps in the national return migration infrastructure—particularly in terms of coordination, resource management, and implementation capacity. Far from being an isolated case, the OTE's situation reflects systemic difficulties that hinder the effectiveness of reintegration policies in Tunisia.⁷⁷

Beyond this example, such gaps are common in how international donors, national governments, and local organizations align their priorities. While international donors,

such as the European Union, often focus on border control and quick returns, humanitarian and local organizations prioritize the sustainable reintegration of migrants.⁷⁸ These differing goals create challenges for coordination and delay the implementation of effective initiatives. Furthermore, reintegration programs are often designed without a deep understanding of local needs; making them less relevant to the people they are meant to support. These problems, whether financial, organizational, or strategic, highlight the need for better coordination between actors, realistic planning, and ongoing evaluation to address these weaknesses and achieve the intended goals.

7. Conclusion

Despite the wealth and diversity of data collected on the actors, infrastructures, and practices involved in welcoming and supporting returning Tunisian migrants, grey areas and blind spots warrant ongoing research. As with all third countries, migrant readmission remains a sensitive issue. However, since the outbreak of the Tunisian migration crisis in February 2023, topics such as sub-Saharan migration to Tunisia and the return of Tunisians have become particularly sensitive, especially for the authorities. In both instances, the authorities are suspected of playing into the hands of Europeans by failing to protect migrants' human rights and, importantly, of having signed agreements that facilitate the expulsion of Tunisians from Europe. Highly aggressive campaigns have been launched by NGOs and websites criticising the authorities for proven violations of sub-Saharan migrants' human rights—including arrests, arbitrary detentions, abandonment in the desert, and pushbacks. The authorities deny these claims and refuse to view repression against sub-Saharan migrants or the readmission of Tunisians expelled from Europe as policies that favour European interests, neglecting to consider Tunisia's or Africa's broader interests. The increasing tension among authorities regarding these issues explains their reluctance to collaborate or provide unrestricted access to information. Despite repeated requests, the Tunisian authorities have never, for example, disclosed details about European funding for training and equipping security services or the maritime guard. Access to airports—such as Enfida-Hammamet and Tabarka—for the readmission of Tunisians deported from Europe remains highly restricted.

Another challenge for research in this module is the interference in the use of equipment and infrastructure for return, interception at sea, and even removal to the frontiers in the desert or at borders.

Ultimately, research on the subject of RMI reveals the extent of the involvement and mobilization of various actors and organizations in this component of the border regime: returns. With one or two exceptions, no any distancing recorded from the efficiency or usefulness of the projects that mobilize this infrastructure.

References

Boubakri (H), Potot (S), « Migrations et révolution en Tunisie », HAL, 19/05/2016, p.3-4.

EuroMed Rights. Return Mania. Mapping policies and practices in the EuroMed Region, March 2021: https://euromedrights.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/EN_INTRO-Report_Migration-1.pdf

European Court of Auditors, special Report. Frontex's support to external border management: not sufficiently effective to date, 2021, https://www.eca.europa.eu/Lists/ECADocuments/SR21_08/SR_Frontex_EN.pdf

http://www.courdescomptes.nat.tn/Fr/thematiques_58_4_0_3_10_0000_00_00_Office%20des%20Tunisiens%20%C3%A0%20l%E2%80%99Etranger_100

INFO MIGRANTS. Le programme "Tounesna", ou comment aider les Tunisiens expulsés d'Europe à retrouver une vie au pays, 02/06/2023 <https://www.infomigrants.net/fr/post/49389/le-programme-tounesna-ou-comment-aider-les-tunisiens-expulses-deurope-a-retrouver-une-vie-au-pays>

IOM Glossary on Migration, 2019, <https://www.migrationdataportal.org/themes/return-migration#definition>

National Institute of statistics, The Tunisia -HIMS National Survey on International Migration: <http://www.migration.nat.tn/images/pdf/2022/Tunisia-Hims-en-opt.pdf>

Observatoire National de la Migration (2023). Profils et trajectoires des migrants Tunisiens de retour. 204 p. <http://www.migration.nat.tn/ar/publications/etudes-et-recherche/profils-et-trajectoires-des-migrants-tunisiens-de-retour>

Parlement européen, Pourquoi Migrer? Les raisons derrière les migrations, 3/7/2020 :

<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/fr/article/20200624STO81906/pourquoi-migrer-les-raisons-derriere-la-migration>

ProGreS Migration (Phase III) : Soutenir la réinsertion durable des Tunisiens et Tunisiennes de retour en Tunisie. Expertise individuelle en Suivi-évaluation, Redevabilité et Apprentissage (SERA) Février 2024 <https://expertise-france.gestmax.fr/expertise-france/public-files/tdr-expertise-perlee-sera-progres-migration-iii-vf1707834738891.pdf>

REACH and Mercy Corps, Tunisia, Country of emigration and return. Migration dynamics since 2011. December 2018:

[https://www.mercycorps.org/sites/default/files/2020-01/Tunisia country of emigration and return.pdf](https://www.mercycorps.org/sites/default/files/2020-01/Tunisia%20country%20of%20emigration%20and%20return.pdf)

Sustainable Reintegration of returning Migrants. A better home coming, OECD 2020: [file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/5fee55b3-en%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/5fee55b3-en%20(1).pdf)

Xiang, B., & Lindquist, J. (2014). Migration infrastructure. *International migration review*, 48, S122-S148.

¹ See the *Report of the national survey on international migration Tunisia-HIMS*,

<https://www.ins.tn/sites/default/files-ftp3/files/publication/pdf/Rapport%20de%20l%27enqu%C3%AAte%20nationale%20sur%20la%20migration%20internationale%20Tunisia-HIMS.pdf>

²<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/fr/article/20200624STO81906/pourquoi-migrer-les-raisons-derriere-la-migration>

³https://publications.iom.int/system/files/pdf/impacts-of-COVID-19-gender_1.pdf.

⁴<https://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/revolution-and-political-transition-tunisia-migration-game-changer>

⁵<https://dgap.org/en/research/publications/walking-tightrope-tunisia>.

⁶<https://dgap.org/en/research/publications/walking-tightrope-tunisia>.

⁷<https://www.infomigrants.net/fr/post/44985/employees-wanted-in-europe-a-tunisian-perspective-22#:~:text=Tunisia%20has%20been%20going%20through,like%20the%20only%20way%20forward..>

⁸*Report of the national survey on international migration Tunisia-HIMS*,

<https://www.ins.tn/sites/default/files-ftp3/files/publication/pdf/Rapport%20de%20l%27enqu%C3%AAte%20nationale%20sur%20la%20migration%20internationale%20Tunisia-HIMS.pdf>

⁹[https://www.mercycorps.org/sites/default/files/2020-01/Tunisia country of emigration and return.pdf](https://www.mercycorps.org/sites/default/files/2020-01/Tunisia%20country%20of%20emigration%20and%20return.pdf)

-
- ¹⁰<https://www.ohchr.org/en/migration/migrants-vulnerable-situations>
- ¹¹<https://www.iom.int/news/growing-insecurity-tripoli-endangers-displaced-civilians-and-migrants-armed-clashes-enter-second-month>
- ¹²<https://mixedmigration.org/eight-things-we-learned-about-migrant-returns-and-reintegration/#:~:text=Many%20migrants%20feel%20pressured%20to,notion%20of%20%E2%80%9Cvoluntary%E2%80%9D%20return.>
- ¹³<https://worldmigrationreport.iom.int/msite/wmr-2024-interactive/>
- ¹⁴<https://www.ins.tn/sites/default/files-ftp3/files/publication/pdf/Rapport%20de%20l%27enqu%C3%AAte%20nationale%20sur%20la%20migration%20internationale%20Tunisie-HIMS.pdf>
- ¹⁵IOM Glossary on Migration, 2019, <https://www.migrationdataportal.org/themes/return-migration#definition>
- ¹⁶<https://www.migrationdataportal.org/themes/return-migration#definition>
- ¹⁷<https://www.frontex.europa.eu/return-and-reintegration/return-operations/return-operations/>
- ¹⁸EuroMed Rights. Return Mania. Mapping policies and practices in the EuroMed Region. April 2021. https://euromedrights.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/EN_Chapter-4-Italy-Tunisia-1.pdf
- ¹⁹ - https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2020-0238_EN.pdf
- ²⁰REACH and Mercy Corps, Tunisia, Country of emigration and return. Migration dynamics since 2011. December 2018: https://www.mercycorps.org/sites/default/files/2020-01/Tunisia_country_of_emigration_and_return.pdf
- ²¹ Ibid.
- ²²<https://www.webdo.tn/fr/actualite/national/la-france-a-expulse-1200-tunisiens-en-2021/133369>
- ²³https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2020-0238_EN.pdf
- ²⁴https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2020-0238_EN.pdf
- ²⁵ Ibid.
- ²⁶<https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2024/forced-return-monitoring-systems-2024-update>
- ²⁷Should they stay or should they go? Frontex’s fundamental rights dilemma <https://www.sieps.se/en/publications/2022/should-they-stay-or-should-they-go-frontexs-fundamental-rights-dilemma/>
- ²⁸EuroMed Rights. Return Mania. Mapping policies and practices in the EuroMed Region. April 2021. https://euromedrights.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/EN_Chapter-4-Italy-Tunisia-1.pdf
- ²⁹<https://www.mignex.org/sites/default/files/2023-02/mbp-d053-migration-relevant-policies-in-tunisia-v2-2023-02-22.pdf>
- ³⁰ - <https://www.mignex.org/sites/default/files/2023-02/mbp-d053-migration-relevant-policies-in-tunisia-v2-2023-02-22.pdf>
- ³¹ The Tunisian Ministry of Interior didn’t provide to the GAP’S team the information’s and data about the expelled Tunisian migrants readmitted to Tunisia.
- ³² - Ibid.
- ³³ EuroMed Rights. Return Mania. Mapping policies and practices in the EuroMed Region. April 2021. https://euromedrights.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/EN_Chapter-4-Italy-Tunisia-1.pdf
- ³⁴ Tunisian Forum for Economic and Social Rights, Illegal immigrants and the deportation from Italy. Socio - anthropological study, <https://ftdes.net/rapports/etude.rapatricie.en.pdf>

³⁵*Ibid.*

³⁶ REACH and Mercy corps: Tunisia, Country of emigration and return. Migration dynamics since 2011. December 2018. https://www.mercycorps.org/sites/default/files/2020-01/Tunisia_country_of_emigration_and_return.pdf

³⁷*Ibid.*

³⁸ Tunisian Forum for Economic and Social Rights, Illegal immigrants and the deportation from Italy. Socio-anthropological study, <https://ftdes.net/rapports/etude.rapatrie.en.pdf>

³⁹ REACH and Mercy corps: Tunisia, Country of emigration and return. Migration dynamics since 2011. December 2018.

https://www.mercycorps.org/sites/default/files/2020-01/Tunisia_country_of_emigration_and_return.pdf

⁴⁰See <https://www.social.gov.tn/fr/organisation>

⁴¹https://www.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd1486/files/2018-07/Les_migrations_humaines_final.pdf

⁴²<https://www.emploi.nat.tn/fo/Fr/global.php?menu1=15>

⁴³<http://www.migration.nat.tn/ar/presentation/missions>

⁴⁴ The ICMPD supports the development of return migration infrastructure by assisting governments in designing sustainable return and reintegration programs, improving legal frameworks, and facilitating cooperation between countries for effective return policies. It also provides capacity building and technical expertise to enhance reintegration support systems. (<https://www.icmpd.org/about-us/about-icmpd>)

⁴⁵<https://www.giz.de/en/aboutgiz/profile.html>

⁴⁶<https://www.giz.de/en/worldwide/82985.html>

⁴⁸<https://tunisia.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd11056/files/documents/brochure%20projet%20de%20retour%20%E2%80%A6%20projet%20d%27avenir%20%28A4%29.pdf>

⁴⁹We should note that we wrote and sent through various channels about ten letters to the IOM office in Tunisia inviting them to be part of the Panel of Experts and Stakeholders of the GAPs project and also to obtain data on the returns of Tunisians from the Schengen area or on the repatriation of sub-Saharan migrants from Tunisia to their countries of origin. They never responded to our requests.

⁵⁰<https://www.social.gov.tn/fr/migration-et-tunisiens-%C3%A0-l%C3%A9tranger>

⁵¹<https://www.social.gov.tn/fr/migration-et-tunisiens-%C3%A0-l%C3%A9tranger>

⁵² <https://news.gnet.tn/tunisie-une-rencontre-autour-du-secretaire-detat-aux-pme-pour-la-relance-de-linvestissement-et-de-linitiative-privee/>

⁵³<https://www.omct.org/fr/membres-du-reseau/ligue-tunisienne-pour-la-d%C3%A9fense-des-droits-de-lhomme-ltdh>

⁵⁴<https://medecinsdumonde.be/regions/tunisie>

⁵⁵ Bel Haj Zekri (A), « La migration du retour en Tunisie », Rapport d'analyse MIREM-AR 2007/04, MIREM Project, 2004, p. 13-14.

(https://cadmus.eui.eu/bitstream/handle/1814/7985/MIREM_AR_2007_04.pdf?sequence=1)

⁵⁶https://expertise-france.gestmax.fr/_expertise_france/public_files/tdr-expert-e-s-e-ct.pdf

⁵⁷<https://www.ofii.fr/en/reintegration-of-tunisians-in-their-country-the-tounesna-scheme-opens-a-new-branch/>

⁵⁸https://www.ofii.fr/en/reintegration-of-tunisians-in-their-country-the-tounesna-scheme-opens-a-new-branch/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

⁵⁹<https://expertise-france.gestmax.fr/expertise-france/public-files/tdr-expertise-perlee-sera-progres-migration-iii-vf1707834738891.pdf>

⁶⁰<https://www.infomigrants.net/fr/post/49389/le-programme-tounesna-ou-comment-aider-les-tunisiens-expulses-deurope-a-retrouver-une-vie-au-pays>

⁶¹ <https://tunisiaplus.org/tounesna/>

⁶² <https://inkyfada.com/fr/2024/06/24/expulsions-compagnie-italie-tunisie/>

⁶³<https://www.garantenazionaleprivatiliberta.it/gnpl/resources/cms/documents/40c2388838a4b53ef9ecb6f82118d188.pdf>

⁶⁴https://www.mercycorps.org/sites/default/files/2020-01/Tunisia_country_of_emigration_and_return.pdf

⁶⁵https://euromedrights.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/EN_INTRO-migration-research.pdf

⁶⁶<https://www.startfinder.de/fr/experiences/tun-how-i-became-an-independent-woman>

⁶⁷<https://ecdpm.org/application/files/2516/5546/8598/Tunisia-Possibilities-Reform-Implementation-Migrant-Reception-Protection-ECDPM-study-November-2020.pdf>

⁶⁸<https://w2eu.info/media/pages/countries/germany/deportation/672393118c-1716037674/abschiebungen-englisch-digital.pdf>

<https://w2eu.info/media/pages/countries/germany/deportation/5780dd989d-1718118787/abschiebungen-arabisch-digital.pdf>

⁶⁹<https://lac.iom.int/en/blogs/coming-home-can-be-harder-leaving-psychosocial-challenges-being-returnee>

⁷⁰In 2015, the Commission introduced the "Integrated Return Management System" (IRMS) to enhance practical collaboration among Member States and with third countries. This initiative initially sought to strengthen the connections between EU-funded networks dedicated to return and readmission.

(https://www.eca.europa.eu/lists/ecadocuments/ap20_07/ap_migrant_return_policy_en.pdf)

⁷¹AMIF is set up for the period 2021-2027. It aims to strengthen national capacities and enhance migration management procedures, while promoting greater solidarity and responsibility-sharing among Member States. (https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/funding/asylum-migration-and-integration-funds/asylum-migration-and-integration-fund-2021-2027_en)

⁷²https://www.eca.europa.eu/Lists/ECADocuments/SR21_17/SR_Readmission-cooperation_EN.pdf

⁷³<https://www.startfinder.de/en/advisory-centre/german-tunisian-centre-jobs-migration-and-reintegration-tunis>

⁷⁴<https://www.thebigwall.org/>

⁷⁵Matteo Garavoglia AriannaPoletti (2022) Tunisia, The Coastguard Wall:<https://irpimedia.irpi.eu/thebigwall-tunisia-muro-della-guardia-costiera/>

⁷⁶Matteo Garavoglia (2024). The role of European funding for migration in the violent practices of Tunisian security authorities. In FTDES. 17p. <https://ftdes.net/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/LE-ROLE-DES-FINANCEMENTS-EUROPEENS.pdf>

⁷⁷http://www.courdescomptes.nat.tn/Fr/thematiques_58_4_0_3_10_0000_0000_Office%20des%20Tunisie%20C3%A0%20l%E2%80%99Etranger_100

⁷⁸These NGO initiatives do not represent fully achieved examples of "sustainable return," but rather alternative models of reintegration that are more humane and participatory, aiming to fill the gaps left by official mechanisms. They illustrate a potential for sustainability, but not yet a guaranteed one.